

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SYNERGISM STRATEGY, SYNERGISM EFFECT IN COMPANIES' MERGER OR AMALGAMATION

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Abstract

Synergism is one of the possible key components of corporate-level strategy. The main problem in developing a synergy strategy is related to the contradiction between management flexibility and synergy: increasing management flexibility reduces potential profits and potential synergism. At the same time, it is believed that the main danger of this strategy is the lack of flexibility, as well as possible compromises and delays in decision-making. These disadvantages can negate all the value advantages.

Keywords: Synergism, strategy, management, business, synergism effect, M&A transactions, technologies

Synergism strategy - a strategy for gaining competitive advantages by combining two or more business units (economic substructures) into one hand. The presence of the effect of synergism and the ability to manage this effect creates a specific competitive advantage, which is realized at the level of the enterprise in general and which, ultimately, manifests itself in reducing the level of costs in various product markets or in acquiring unique properties by products. Synergism strategy involves increasing the efficiency of performance through the joint use of resources (synergy of technologies and costs), market infrastructure (joint sale) or scopes of activities (synergy of planning and management). Therefore, the importance of the synergism strategy is that it helps to obtain higher profitability of production with interconnected business units rather than when they are managed separately.

American economists W.King and D.Cleland consider synergism an important element in choosing, developing and detailing a strategy. They note that synergistic effects – no matter how potentially large they – will not happen by themselves, they must be planned and exploited. This is possible if synergies are identified, defined and invested in reasonable and prudent plans. The synergistic effect is most clearly manifested at the portfolio (corporate) strategy level, but is also possible within a single business unit. Economic practice shows that the effect of joint activities is always higher than the simple sum of individual efforts, due to the potential of cooperation and interaction.

B.Karloff notes that many managers avoid using the term "Synergism" (Synergy) and use synonyms that differ only slightly in meaning. Such synonyms are the concepts of "strategic leverage", "interconnections", "rationalization", "value advantage".

The term was first introduced by I.Ansoff to evaluate the relationship between the types of activities within a company. According to him, "in the original sense, the concept of synergism was the transition from the principle of economy of scale of production in the manufacturing industry to the broader principle of stra-

tegic economy, the source of which is the mutual support of various strategic business units". The market conditions for the use of this strategy are joint ownership of resources and scopes of activity or voluntary pooling of efforts. It is this synergistic effect that managers refer to when justifying the acquisition or merger of businesses.

However, the synergistic effect is an extremely complex phenomenon, its obtaining depends on the successful combination of many different elements. Omitting even one or part of these elements may eliminate the possibility of achieving such an effect. To avoid this, it is desirable to introduce a collective discussion of this event by specialists with appropriate knowledge in the fields under study. This eliminates thinking at the level of desires and expectations that is so characteristic of synergy-seeking strategies. In addition, the management of the enterprise should be organized in such a way as to achieve the realization of potential synergies by the managers of the business units. Otherwise, a negative synergistic effect appears. I. Ansoff believes that managers should be guided by the following considerations when choosing a synergy strategy:

It is believed that the higher the expected volatility of external factors and the severity of competition, the higher the importance of synergy for success.

The main problem in developing a synergy strategy is related to the contradiction between management flexibility and synergy: increasing management flexibility reduces potential profits and potential synergism. At the same time, it is believed that the main danger of this strategy is the lack of flexibility, as well as possible compromises and delays in decision-making. These disadvantages can negate all the value advantages.

It should be noted that this strategy is the basis for the creation of various unions, alliances, financial and industrial groups both at the national and international levels. On a national scale, the result of such a strategy is the creation of different types of marketing networks, allowing to use the synergistic effect of the interaction between production and sales.

The synergism effect should be considered as a tool for selecting prospective M&A transactions. If it is necessary to choose from several options of the company - for a takeover from objects, it is considered optimal to choose the target company, the acquisition of which ensures the achievement of the greatest synergistic effect by the company-buyer. If the target company is the only candidate for such a transaction, then the decision to acquire it will depend on whether it is possible to achieve a positive synergy effect in principle (in case of a positive answer, the transaction will be recognized as promising and appropriate to conclude) or, conversely, taking into account all the peculiarities of the transaction and based on the results of evaluating all possible synergies in this situation and comparing them with the transaction costs, the company finally reaches a negative value of synergy.

Thus, synergism is one of the possible key components of corporate-level strategy. I.Ansoff defined the

economic basis of synergism (the possibility that the result of the joint efforts of several business units will exceed the final performance of their independent activities). The synergy equation is partly based on economies of scale. For example, it is possible to reduce the costs of two business units by increasing the load factor of a particular company, by using common staff or by combining sales efforts.

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